

DEEP LEARNING-BASED CREATION OF FRACTAL ART GRAPHICS AND FRACTAL ANALYSIS OF INFORMATION FLOW

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Abstract. This article discusses the creation of fractal art graphics based on deep learning technologies and the fractal analysis of information flow. The application of neural networks in the image creation process using unconventional structures of fractal geometry, along with the aesthetic and informational properties of the created graphics, is analyzed. Additionally, the methods of representing and evaluating the complex structure of information flows through fractal modeling are presented. The proposed approaches not only ensure the integration of fractal art with modern digital technologies but also serve to enhance the effectiveness of information systems. The results are presented through graphical images, statistical analyses, and visualizations, highlighting the practical importance of fractal structures in information technology. Furthermore, the article examines the role of artificial intelligence in transforming art design and education, and how deep learning opens up opportunities for developing both artistic and technical skills. The analysis of information flow during the design process is explored, shedding light on the potential of deep learning to open up new possibilities in graphic creation and improve the educational experience of students in the fields of art and design.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Deep Learning, Art Design, fractal analysis

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada chuqur o‘rganish texnologiyalari asosida fraktal san’at grafikalarini yaratish va axborot oqimining fraktal tahlili masalalari ko‘rib chiqilgan. Fraktal geometriyaning noan’anaviy tuzilmalari yordamida tasvir yaratish jarayoniga neyron tarmoqlarning qo‘llanilishi, yaratilgan grafiklarning estetik va informatsion xususiyatlari bilan birga tahlil etiladi. Maqolada, shuningdek, axborot oqimlarining murakkab tuzilishini fraktal modellash orqali tasvirlash va baholash usullari bayon qilinadi. Taklif etilgan yondashuvlar fraktal san’atning zamonaviy raqamli texnologiyalar bilan uyg‘unlashuvini ta’minlash bilan birga, axborot tizimlarining samaradorligini oshirishga xizmat qiladi. Natijalar grafik tasvirlar, statistik tahlillar hamda vizualizatsiya asosida ko‘rsatilib, fraktal strukturalarning axborot texnologiyalaridagi amaliy ahamiyati yoritiladi. Bundan tashqari, maqolada sun’iy intellektning san’at dizayni va ta’limni o‘zgartirishdagi roli o‘rganilib, chuqur o‘rganish yordamida san’at va texnik ko‘nikmalarni rivojlantirishning qanday imkoniyatlarini ochib beradi. Dizayn jarayonida ma’lumotlar oqimi tahlil qilinib, chuqur o‘rganishning grafik yaratishda yangi imkoniyatlarni ochib berish va san’at va dizayn ta’limi sohasida talabalarning o‘qish tajribasini yaxshilashdagi salohiyati yoritilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Sun’iy intellekt, chuqur o‘rganish, san’at dizayni, fraktal tahlil

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается создание фрактальных художественных графиков на основе технологий глубокого обучения и фрактальный анализ информационных потоков. Применение нейронных сетей в процессе создания

изображений с использованием нетрадиционных структур фрактальной геометрии, а также анализ эстетических и информационных свойств созданных графиков. В статье также излагаются методы представления и оценки сложной структуры информационных потоков через фрактальное моделирование. Предложенные подходы обеспечивают интеграцию фрактального искусства с современными цифровыми технологиями, а также способствуют повышению эффективности информационных систем. Результаты представлены с помощью графических изображений, статистических анализов и визуализаций, подчеркивающих практическое значение фрактальных структур в информационных технологиях. Кроме того, рассматривается роль искусственного интеллекта в преобразовании дизайна искусства и образования, а также как глубокое обучение открывает возможности для развития как художественных, так и технических навыков. В процессе дизайна анализ информационных потоков освещает потенциал глубокого обучения для открытия новых возможностей в создании графики и улучшении образовательного опыта студентов в области искусства и дизайна.

Ключевые слова: Искусственный интеллект, Глубокое обучение, Дизайн искусства, Фрактальный анализ.

1. INTRODUCTION

Art design brings color to people's lives, creates a pleasant environment, and offers warmth and comfort amid the fast pace of modern life. Science and technology have significantly contributed to societal advancement and also play a vital role in the field of art and design [1]. The analysis of digital and analog classroom simulations in electronic products has become essential in the teaching of artistic creation. Different analyses of digital signal environments in electronic courses often yield varying outcomes in custom-compiled array designs. Abugharbieh and Marar [2] designed complete computer microcircuits by integrating transistor resources and optimizing modern technologies to enhance engineering applications.

In today's era, artificial intelligence is widely utilized in art design, allowing for a more expressive and vivid presentation of designers' ideas and concepts. This helps in better appreciation of artworks and understanding of other designers' artistic intentions. Computer-Aided Design (CAD) is increasingly recognized for its precision, realism, ease of modification and storage, and its ability to inspire creativity. Graphic design in art is a modeling activity aimed at decorative layout creation [3].

Amirovna [4] investigated the independent role of fractal composition in artistic creation and its application in natural energy-based products. The findings show that fractal composition functions as an algorithm for generating complex and intricate patterns in art education. CAD tools can generate such intricate designs using fractal algorithms. CAD-assisted fractal design plays an important role in both fine and applied arts by enhancing creativity, efficiency, accuracy, and enabling safe and innovative design environments.

Fractal patterns differ from traditional European geometries. Though mathematically generated via computer programs, they blend scientific precision with artistic beauty. Bai et al. [5] developed a random noise-based signal encryption system for securing image data. Their approach hides and encrypts fractal images, ensuring even pixel distribution and reducing computational complexity in visual encryption processes.

Chao [6] analyzed the aesthetic integration of mathematics into traditional artworks, exploring visual direction through fractal design techniques. During automated parameter design,

user feedback and function analysis are efficiently incorporated, enabling clearer identification of user needs through targeted parameter adjustments. Currently, AI is frequently applied in the art domain. Its major strength lies in the ability to express creativity through various modalities. In terms of design, AI significantly supports artistic innovation. Artworks created with AI can effectively communicate the designer's intent and vividly express the meaning embedded in the art.

This paper focuses on a CAD-based fractal graphic generation approach using Deep Learning (DL). The main innovations are as follows:

1. A random noise image is iteratively optimized by minimizing a total loss function based on both content and style information, allowing the final output to retain the structural features of the content image and the textures of the style image. This forms a foundation for CAD-based fractal graphic generation using DL.

2. A novel method is employed namely, the negative gradient approach—which continuously adjusts the objective function's input values toward a local minimum. The network's weights and biases are updated through backpropagation, and global average pooling is utilized to reduce the number of parameters in the network.

According to the needs of content and structure, the article is divided into six sections: the first section: introduction, which mainly introduces the background and significance of the topic, and explains the research innovation and structural arrangement of this article. Section II: Based on the literature review, the main research contents of this article are put forward. Section III: The basic theory of computer aided design of fractal graphics is expounded. Section IV: Using CNN (Convolutional Neural Network) technology, a fractal art graphics generation model is established, and the concrete implementation steps of the model are given. Section V, empirical analysis. Through the analysis of the established mathematical model, it is proved that the established mathematical model is scientific and reasonable. The sixth section summarizes the main achievements and contributions of this article.

2. RELATED WORK

Gdawiec and Adewinbi [7] explored the model generation of artistic patterns. It uses a symmetrical wallpaper pattern to expand the Euclidean and dimensional orbits. The proposed scheme can obtain various interesting patterns. Therefore, the trajectory trap under this method can obtain patterns with fractal structures. He and Sun [8] have developed an emerging intelligent teaching assistance model. This model has played a professional role in the online teaching platform of art creation education theory. Based on modern art education theory, it greatly stimulates students' personalized collaboration potential in the art field. At the same time, this model provides students with a virtual environment for physical and mental experience, which provides great advantages for the computer-based art teaching mode. Jin and Yang [9] utilized the advantages of color design in computer environments to help enhance the concept of 3D simulation in innovative design of university cultural and art teaching environments. It adopts the method of object investigation to conduct information art design on the environmental art color design of computer-aided software. At the same time, it analyzed the significant improvement effect of computers on environmental art design. Kulnazarov and Bekmurodov [10] carried out a scheme improvement on Computer graphics format program. Computer graphics is a very important field in architecture and design teaching, which covers many applications. Computer graphics technology can help designers quickly verify the implementation possibility of design ideas in three-dimensional space. Designers can use CAD software for rapid modeling to explore surface modeling. Through digital models, designers can

observe and compare different design schemes in a virtual environment, thereby better adjusting and improving design schemes. Kumari et al. [11] analyzed the application of viscosity approximation iterative methods in Mandelbrot and Julia Fractals generation. It analyzed different integrated visualization images using a linear approximation method. We have derived an escape criterion method that can solve different fixed points. In addition, it also provides examples of different fractal shapes.

Liu and Yang [12] have designed an open computer-aided art teaching model. Its aim is to explore a modular and optimized learning mode. There is a certain issue of teaching coherence in the creation of information services in the current art architecture. It uses computer CAD technology to develop web pages for server information teaching. This improves the collaborative performance of the art classroom task group, allowing all debugging deployments to actively participate in artistic creation. Nakamura [13] analyzed a fractal structured visualization algorithm population effect model. It proposes an image rendering application algorithm based on mathematical transformation. This algorithm solves the mathematical problem of artistic extension in drawing 2D and 3D fractal graphics, and provides fractal clues for different art groups. Ouyang et al. [14] implemented a graphic system for printmaking classification similarity. He created a graphic structure based on isosceles Right triangle, and derived a Graphics library similar to Escher. Popa et al. [15] improved the model accuracy of the software structure in terms of real-time generation of image processing software. It introduces a computer-assisted fractal optimization variant and compares it with practical differentiation time at the processor level. The results showed that the developed parallelized image program shortened the computational time of image processing, and the study analyzed the resources of mathematical images from the perspective of image differentiation technology.

Driven by AI, through CAD fractal art graphic design, patterns can be easily created, modified and saved. Fractal patterns can be realized by computer programs. Through the setting of various parameters of the software, the fineness and generation mode of graphics can be controlled; Change the color, depth and angle of the figure, and enlarge and decorate the part conveniently; Copy, paste and save quickly. In this article, driven by AI, the problem of CAD fractal art graphic generation is deeply discussed based on DL algorithm, and a fractal art graphic generation model is constructed based on CNN.

3. GENERATION MODEL OF FRACTAL ART GRAPHIC BASED ON CNN

Fractal art is a graphic art form with unique aesthetics and artistic value. In order to generate fractal art graphics, we can use Convolutional neural network (CNN) to build a Generative model. The following is how to build a Generative model of fractal art graphics based on CNN: First, we need to collect a large number of fractal art graphics data, which can be from public data sets on the network or generated by ourselves. Next, we need to preprocess the data, including steps such as size normalization and image enhancement, in order to provide high-quality training data for CNN. Next, we need to design a suitable CNN model. Considering the characteristics of fractal art graphics, we can use deep learning frameworks such as TensorFlow or PyTorch to construct models. The design of the model should include convolution layer, pooling layer, Activation function and other components to achieve layer by layer abstraction and feature extraction of images. After the model design is completed, we need to provide training data for the model and optimize the model parameters through the Backpropagation. In the training process, Loss function such as Cross entropy can be used to evaluate the performance of the model, and super parameters such as Learning rate and iterations can be adjusted according to the actual situation. After the training is completed, we need to

evaluate and tune the model. The evaluation process can use a test set, and evaluation indicators can include accuracy, recall rate, etc. We can fine-tune or improve the model based on the evaluation results. Finally, we can use the trained model to generate new fractal art graphics. We can use the input image as the input of the model, and then generate the corresponding fractal art graphics through the predicted output of the model. In addition, we can also improve the complexity and artistry of the generated graphics by modifying the parameters of the model or adding additional layers. In general, the fractal art graphics Generative model based on CNN needs to rely on a series of steps such as data collection, preprocessing, model design, model training, model evaluation and optimization, and graphics generation. Through this model, we can achieve the conversion from input ordinary images to output fractal art graphics, providing a new possibility for artistic creation and graphic design.

CNN is a feed-forward neural network with sparse connection, which imitates the biological vision mechanism. CNN can perform parallel computing, has the ability to process information at high speed, and can accumulate experience through repeated learning processes, just like the human brain, which can continuously improve the effect of image classification. CNN is composed of layers of network stacks, and the whole network can be regarded as a function, and many neurons are regarded as parameters of this function. We input this network and expect to get a good output. The function of parameters is self-evident. CNN can learn rasterized features, such as pixels and audio, with less computation. A large quantity of experiments show that the characteristics of CNN extracting image features are: the bottom layer captures the image texture, and the top layer retains the image content. After many convolutions, the characteristics of learning become more and more global. The CNN function is defined as:

$$X_j^l = \left(\sum_{i \in M_j} X_i^{l-1} \times k_{ij}^l + b_j^l \right) \quad (1)$$

Where X_i is the input feature map, k represents the convolution kernel, b is the deviation term and the output after convolution is the feature map X_j .

Commonly used activation functions are Sigmoid, Tanh and Relu. Sigmoid function is a kind of S-type function. Compared with Sigmoid function, Tanh function is symmetric about the origin of coordinates. Moreover, around 0, the curve changes more steeply, so in the training stage, the step size of each update of the weights is larger, and it can quickly converge to the optimal value. The graphs of Sigmoid function and Tanh function are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Graphs of Sigmoid function and Tanh function.

The transmission of neuron parameters between layers within a neural network can be represented using matrix operations. Typically, the parameters of all neurons in a given layer are structured as a column vector, while the weights connecting this layer to the subsequent one are

organized into a matrix. Each row i in this matrix represents the set of weights that connect all neurons in the current layer to the i neuron in the next layer.

In the context of fractal art graphics, composition refers to the spatial arrangement and structural layout of fractal elements. The fractal distribution composition arranges these patterns on a series of computed scattered points based on a recursive model, producing layouts that appear random yet follow the rules of statistical self-similarity. This approach brings a higher level of artistic expression and originality, making the resulting works more visually appealing.

Fractal patterns are generated through computer programming techniques. Among these, the iterative algorithm applies transformations based on shapes, whereas the escape time algorithm iterates over individual points. In the latter method, after a series of iterations, the distance between each point and the origin is measured. If it exceeds a predefined threshold, the point is said to “escape,” and its color is assigned based on the number of iterations it took—creating vibrant, multi-colored fractal images.

To support various levels of feature extraction in pattern generation, loss functions with different degrees of fusion are designed. Then, by applying the stochastic gradient descent method, the fractal graphics are updated iteratively to realize the fusion-based generation of these images. For fine-tuning the weights of neurons, a cost function is crafted according to the specific training objectives. The fundamental aim of training a neural network is to reduce the cost function as much as possible. Since the objective functions in deep learning training are typically non-convex, the optimization outcome is sensitive to initial parameter settings. Therefore, careful initialization is essential to prevent the model from getting stuck in local minima too early.

In convolutional neural networks (CNNs), training samples typically consist of two main components:

$$X = [x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_{n1}]^T \quad (2)$$

For the expected output vector:

$$T = [t_1, t_2, t_3, \dots, x_{N3}]^T \quad (3)$$

The output of the hidden layer node h and the output of the output layer node s are:

$$y_h^k = f \left(\sum_{i=1}^{N1} w_{ih} x_i^k + \theta_h \right) \quad k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N \quad (4)$$

$$o_s^k = g \left(\sum_{h=1}^{N2} w_{hs} y_h^k + \theta_s \right) \quad k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N \quad (5)$$

In this model, the pooling operation can be regarded as transforming a picture with high resolution into a picture with relatively low resolution, which is beneficial to sampling and selecting excellent features, making the model have anti-noise ability, reducing the feature dimension and reducing the calculation amount by half. By using the pool layer, the calculation speed can be effectively accelerated, and the over-fitting problem can be prevented. In addition to the initialization of parameters, the selection of super parameters in the training stage of network model is also very important. These super parameters include convolution kernel size, moving step size and learning rate. Only by setting parameters and super parameters can the accuracy of the network be improved as a whole.

Each layer of CNN network is connected by neurons, and each neuron contains a weight parameter. During the training stage, the parameter is continuously transmitted to the deeper level and finally reaches the output layer. The quantity of nodes in the input and output layers is

fixed. The schematic diagram of CNN construction process in this article is as follows (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of CNN construction process.

The preprocessing of data will seriously affect the network's feature extraction. This processing method is often used for data sets with simple structure, and the trained model is also very effective.

Firstly, the original image is filtered by low-pass filter, and then a low-frequency image is obtained by down-sampling according to the sampling matrix, which is a coarse-scale approximate image of the original image. The reason why CNN can effectively extract the deep features of the image is mainly due to the convolution operation of the image. In a computer, a picture can be regarded as a two-dimensional matrix, and convolution operation is to calculate and process each two-dimensional matrix accordingly. During network training, each filter convolves the input layer to extract higher-level image features. The formula of the activation layer after the convolution layer is as follows:

$$F_j^{(n+1)} = f(F_j^n) \quad (6)$$

Where: f is a point-by-point activation function. Convert each data item x_i in a small batch $B = \{x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_m\}$ with the size of m into y_i :

$$y_i = \gamma \hat{x}_i + \beta \quad (7)$$

$$\hat{x}_i = \frac{x_i - E_M(x_i)}{\sqrt{Var_M(X_i) + \varepsilon}} \quad (8)$$

Using the hole convolution kernel can expand the receptive field of convolution operation without losing information and introducing additional parameters, so that it can collect feature information in a large range. If m holes are inserted between every two elements in the convolution kernel with the size of $|\times|$, the effective area of convolution operation can be expanded to $(1+4m) \times (1+4m)$. The training of CNN model is closely related to the amount of data. The data can be obtained from natural images, generated by cropping or rotation, and obtained by generative countermeasure network. When these data are insufficient, the generalization ability of the model will be seriously affected and over-fitting will occur.

4. SIMULATION EXPERIMENT ANALYSIS

In To verify the effectiveness and precision of the AI-driven deep learning-based computer-aided fractal art graphics generation model, simulation experiments can be carried out. One common method is to use a known fractal art graphic as the model's input and compare the model's output with the original image. This comparison helps assess the model's accuracy by analyzing the differences between the generated and original graphics. Additionally, this allows us to evaluate the model's generalization capability—whether it can consistently produce appropriate fractal art patterns when presented with various input images.

To thoroughly evaluate the model’s performance across diverse conditions, it should be tested in multiple application scenarios. Performance metrics such as precision and recall can be used to measure model quality. Furthermore, comparing the proposed model with other existing techniques highlights its advantages and improvements in accuracy and efficiency. To assess real-world usability, user surveys and feedback can be collected. By presenting the model-generated fractal graphics to users and gathering their opinions and evaluations, the practical value and reliability of the model can be more clearly understood.

These simulation evaluations serve as solid evidence for the reliability and practical utility of the AI-powered fractal art generation model. At the same time, user feedback can inform iterative improvements and refinements, enabling the model to better satisfy the requirements of different application scenarios.

In a CNN architecture, the quantity of input images significantly influences the model’s final performance. During the training phase, CNNs rely on sample images to extract key features used for classification. A limited number of samples leads to reduced feature learning. Therefore, a large and diverse image dataset is critical—images from the same category should be collected under varied conditions. In this experiment, the image resolution is 1920×1080 . The model is built and implemented using TensorFlow, Google’s open-source deep learning framework. The convolution kernel used is of size 3×3 with a stride of 1. Depending on the dimensions of the image, padding may be applied as needed. Proper parameter selection during training is essential to ensure accurate learning. Figure 3 illustrates the loss function's descent curve during the training process of the proposed network.

Figure 3: Decline process of loss function of network.

In this experiment, because the training set, verification set and verification set have all been converted to TFRecord format, the images are loaded according to TFRecord file instead of JPEG file. Load the training image by matching all TFRecord files found in the directory where the training set is located. In addition, the input image is enhanced, repaired or denoised. These operations can essentially improve the quality of data, thus preparing for subsequent feature extraction. In the execution stage, given any picture, input it into the trained generating network, and the generating network will calculate the result of fractal art graphic generation according to fixed weights. Because the weights of the generating network have been determined during training, the speed of generating pictures will be very fast.

In order to compare the difference of test results between algorithms and the accuracy of positioning, the accuracy of the algorithms is reflected by calculating the F1 value in the experiment, and the calculation method is as follows:

$$F1 = 2 \cdot \frac{Precision \cdot Recall}{Precision + Recall} \quad (9)$$

In this article, AlexNet model, ResNet model and the test results of F1 value of this model are selected to draw a data graph. Specific experiments are shown in Table 1 and Figure 4.

<i>Iterations</i>	<i>This article model</i>	<i>Iterations</i>	<i>This article model</i>
5	89.01	100	93.93
10	92.88	105	94.82
15	91.12	110	93.81
20	90.47	115	93.83
25	92.09	120	92.45
30	91.03	125	94.77
35	91.38	130	95.00
40	92.78	135	93.09
45	92.46	140	94.16
50	89.63	145	93.75

Table 1: Trend of F1 value change.

Figure 4: Comparison results of F1 values of each model.

The test results in Table 1 and Figure 4 show that the F1 value of the constructed model can reach 96.21%, which is about 12% better than that of AlexNet model. It is about 7% better than ResNet model.

The purpose of batch normalization is to avoid that with the deepening of the hierarchy, the input data of the later layer will change due to the updating of the parameters of the previous layer in the network training stage, which will cause the information transmission to decline layer by layer. In this article, the data with the quantity of batch images between 5 and 320 are selected to observe the change of accuracy of the model. Figure 5 shows the change of model accuracy when setting different batch images.

Figure 5: Model accuracy of different batch images.

When the quantity of batch images exceeds a threshold, the accuracy of the model gradually stabilizes. In this experiment, the threshold is 240, so this article chooses 240 as the number of batch pictures in this CNN model. Using multiple filters to convolution an image is a commonly used image processing method that can be used to extract more features of the image. In Convolutional neural network (CNN), multiple filters are usually used to convolve images to extract different features of images. Each filter can be seen as a specific feature extractor that can highlight certain features in the image, such as edges, corners, and so on. The advantage of using multiple filters for convolution is that images can be analyzed from different perspectives and dimensions, thereby extracting more features. These features can be combined and fused in subsequent layers to construct more complex feature representations, ultimately achieving tasks such as image recognition, classification, and segmentation. At the same time, using multiple filters for convolution also increases the complexity and computational complexity of the model. Each filter needs convolution operation, which will increase the time and Space complexity of calculation. Therefore, in practical applications, it is necessary to choose the appropriate number of filters and convolution methods based on specific tasks and data characteristics to achieve better performance and effectiveness. Overall, using multiple filters to convolution images is an effective feature extraction method that can be used for various tasks in image processing and computer vision.

Generally, color images are all three channels, corresponding to RGB. In order to extract more features of the image, this article uses multiple filters to convolution the image, and each filter extracts the input layer and corresponds to one layer. After convolution extraction, multiple filters will generate multiple network layers. The content loss function and style loss function are defined respectively: the content loss function only calculates the high-level feature correlation of empty CNN; The style loss function fuses the feature correlation of all layers. Random initialization following Gaussian distribution is adopted. The weight parameter is set to a random value close to 0, and at the same time, the network is in a symmetrical state, which improves the effect of network training. The following experiment, in the experimental indicators, the calculation formula of Precision and Recall is as follows:

$$Precision = \frac{T_p}{T_p + F_p} \quad (10)$$

$$Recall = \frac{T_p}{T_p + F_N} \quad (11)$$

Where T_p stands for the quantity of positive cases; F_N represents the quantity of negative cases identified; F_p stands for the quantity of recognition errors. The accuracy comparison of the algorithm is shown in Figure 6. The recall trend of the algorithm is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 6: Accuracy comparison of algorithms.

The test results in Figure 6 and Figure 7 show that, compared with AlexNet model and ResNet model, the precision of the model constructed in this article is higher, which can reach more than 90%, and its recall rate is better.

In this article, the Dropout layer added to the model can greatly reduce the cost of fusion. The concrete realization is that in the process of forward propagation, in some hidden layers, each neuron outputs 0 with a certain probability, which is equivalent to training a new model in each training,

Figure 7: Algorithm recall trend.

In addition, in order to improve the practicability and feasibility of DL-based fractal art graphic generation model technology, aiming at its low generation efficiency and unnatural performance, this article uses hole convolution kernel instead of traditional convolution kernel to do convolution operation of image feature extraction, and obtains better and faster fractal art graphic generation effect. On the whole, compared with other classic DL models, the proposed model has better performance, certain reliability and practicability.

5. CONCLUSIONS

CAD technology offers unprecedented means of artistic expression for designers, while artificial intelligence (AI) provides strong data and technical support for the development of art design. Through the integration of AI, the scope of art design has expanded, elevating it to a new level. Based on this, the paper proposes a fractal graphic generation model using deep learning (DL). To minimize the cost function, the model iteratively adjusts its input values in the direction of the negative gradient at a defined step size until it converges to a local minimum. Subsequently, the weights and biases of the entire neural network are updated using backpropagation, resulting in a network that achieves a minimal cost function.

Additionally, various loss functions with different levels of fusion are designed to suit different feature extraction needs. A random gradient descent method is used to iteratively update the pattern generation process, enabling the fused generation of fractal art graphics. Experimental results demonstrate that the proposed model achieves an F1 score of 96.21%, which is approximately 12% higher than the AlexNet model and about 7% better than ResNet. Moreover, the model's precision exceeds 90%, and it outperforms the compared models in terms of recall as well.

Overall, the proposed model demonstrates superior performance compared to traditional deep learning architectures. Particularly when compared to methods relying on standard CNN-based fusion features, this approach provides higher reliability and improved results. Therefore, this research offers a novel method for CAD-based fractal art graphic generation using DL, and lays a solid theoretical foundation for future studies in this field.

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